
On the 1D Infinitely Deep Square Quantum Well

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Abstract: The one-dimensional infinitely deep square quantum well inherited its name from an ordinary rigid box (the properties of the box), and is considered to be one of the most elementary problems in non-relativistic quantum mechanics due to its simplicity. Given the nature of the problem, we discuss several methods and their solutions which are limited to the one-dimensional time-independent Schrödinger equation—1D TISE. We will consider: (i) non-relativistic quantum mechanics, (ii) supersymmetric quantum mechanics (SUSYQM), (iii) fractional quantum mechanics, (iv) q -quantum mechanics, and (v) the q -hypergeometric differential equation. Ultimately, we show by using an appropriate substitution that it is possible to transform the 1D TISE, such that it becomes the q -hypergeometric differential equation. To sum up, the non-compact q -deformed Lie group— $SU_q(1, 1)$ —and Lie algebra— $su_q(1, 1)$ —are described since the former gives the *dynamical group* or the *spectrum generating algebra* of the system.

Keywords: q -hypergeometric equation, fractional quantum mechanics, q -quantum mechanics, supersymmetric quantum mechanics

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1 Introduction

In nonrelativistic quantum mechanics, the one-dimensional time-independent Schrodinger equation (the 1D TISE) describes the dynamics of a quantum particle (for example, an electron which is indivisible) of mass m . If we consider a particle in a rigid box, then simple predictions between classical and quantum mechanics can be compared, along with any realization of the underlying stationary states which give rise to solutions associated with such a problem. In spite of that, there exist an operator that is unbounded, such that no constant S exist,

that satisfies $\|(\frac{-\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{d^2}{dx^2} + V(x))\psi\| \leq S\|\psi\|$. The operator is known as the Hamiltonian operator (denoted by \hat{H}) with its potential $V(x) \in L^1_{loc}(\mathbb{R})$ —the space of locally integrable functions on \mathbb{R} [1].

The norm of \hat{H} , denoted by $\|\hat{H}\|$ is the smallest S possible if the operator were bounded. However, it should be noted that we strictly require \hat{H} to be unbounded and hermitian. Likewise, most operators in quantum mechanics are normal operators as laid out in the spectral theorem. Finally, The Hamiltonian is sometimes refered to as the energy operator in both classical and quantum mechanics—it is the sum of the kinetic

and potential energy of the system.

1.1 1D infinitely deep square quantum well—1D IDSQW

We begin our analysis with the Hamiltonian operator— \hat{H} —and proceed to find exact solutions for the 1D IDSQW. The Hamiltonian¹ for a quantum particle is given by

$$\hat{H} = \frac{-\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{d^2}{dx^2} + V(x), \quad (1.1)$$

with the potential defined as,

$$V(x) = \begin{cases} \infty, & \text{for } x < 0, \\ 0, & \text{for } 0 < x < L, \\ \infty, & \text{for } x > L. \end{cases} \quad (1.2)$$

The customary definition of the wave function— $\Psi(\mathbf{r}, t)$ —is that of a complex function of space and time coordinates. If we take into consideration the modulus of the wave function[2], $|\Psi(\mathbf{r}, t)|^2$, then

$$\begin{aligned} & |\Psi(\mathbf{r}, t)|^2 d\mathbf{r}^3 \\ &= \{\text{The probability density for position!}\}. \end{aligned} \quad (1.3)$$

This is the so-called Born statistical interpretation² of the wave function.

Now due to the separability of the wave function and the time-independent nature of our potential ($V(x) = 0$ inside the well), the 1D TISE is given by

$$\boxed{\frac{d^2\psi(x)}{dx^2} + \frac{2mE}{\hbar^2}\psi(x) = 0} \quad (1.4)$$

where $k^2 = 2mE/\hbar^2$ [3]. Hence we can write the general solution of Eq.(1.4) and determine the constants A and φ using the limiting conditions (or boundary conditions)[4].

The general solution for Eq.(1.4) is

$$\boxed{\psi(x) = A \sin(kx + \varphi)}. \quad (1.5)$$

At $x = 0$ and $x = L$, we must have $\psi(0) = \psi(L) = 0$ which ensures that we do not have a divergent Schrödinger equation. Thus, from Eq.(1.5)

$$\psi(0) = A \sin(\varphi) = 0, \quad (1.6)$$

and

$$\psi(L) = A \sin(kL) = 0. \quad (1.7)$$

Clearly, $\varphi = 0$ and $\sin(kL) = 0$ since A is a non-zero constant. Thus the sine function vanishes for kL [5], it must be the case that

$$k = \frac{n\pi}{L} \quad (n = 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots). \quad (1.8)$$

Therefore, the quantized energy levels are ($n = 1, E_1 = \pi^2\hbar^2/2mL^2$)³ given by

$$E_n = n^2 E_1 \quad (n = 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots) \quad (1.9)$$

and our solution will be of the form,

$$\psi_n(x) = A \sin\left(\frac{n\pi x}{L}\right). \quad (1.10)$$

Of course these functions are orthogonal[6], i.e.,

$$\int_0^L \psi_n(x)^* \psi_m(x) dx = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } m = n \\ 0, & \text{if } m \neq n, \end{cases} \quad (1.11)$$

and this guarantees the determination of the constant, A [7]. Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^L \psi_n(x)^* \psi_m(x) dx &= \int_0^L |\psi_n(x)|^2 dx \\ &= \delta_{nm} \\ &= 1 \quad (n = m) \\ &= \frac{A^2 L}{2}, \end{aligned} \quad (1.12)$$

¹Hermitian operators are normal operators as defined explicitly in the spectral theorem.

² The meaning of the measurement and probability must be specified in order to legitimize Born's interpretation.

³The lowest possible energy is not zero. This is called the zero-point energy.

and we must have

$$\psi_n(x) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{L}} \sin\left(\frac{n\pi x}{L}\right). \quad (1.13)$$

An important and highly noticeable feature in quantum mechanics is its relationship to the classical world. If we consider the ratio of the energies from our spectrum, as $n \rightarrow \infty$, *quantum leaps*—should be thought of as electronic jumps from one discrete energy level to another—become impossible. As a result,

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{E_{n+1} - E_n}{E_n} \right) &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{\Delta E_{n+1,n}}{E_n} \right) \\ &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{2n + 1}{n^2} \right) \\ &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (1.14)$$

Now for $n = 0$, the wavefunction must vanish (with $E_n = 0 = E_0$) and Eq.(1.14) no longer converges. If the energy were zero we would know the precise location of the quantum particle and the uncertainty principle⁴ would be violated. There would be no uncertainty in the particles position or momentum, which makes no sense, therefore $n = 0$ is not allowed.

Let us now consider the number of nodes for a select few of discrete wavefunctions—a node is point where $\psi(x)=0$ whenever $V(x) = 0$ —which are determine from the expression $n - 1$. For example:

$$\psi_1(x) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{L}} \sin\left(\frac{\pi x}{L}\right), \quad (1.15)$$

$$\psi_2(x) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{L}} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi x}{L}\right), \quad (1.16)$$

$$\psi_3(x) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{L}} \sin\left(\frac{3\pi x}{L}\right), \text{ and} \quad (1.17)$$

$$\psi_n(x) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{L}} \sin\left(\frac{n\pi x}{L}\right). \quad (1.18)$$

Thus, it should be obvious that as n increases the sine function oscillates more rapidly. In words, as n gets larger the energy increases and $\psi(x)_n$ becomes more oscillatory. Hence, more nodal points are guaranteed as n gets larger whenever the potential vanishes[7]. The assertions previously made about nodal points are illustrated in **Fig.(1)**, for $L = 1$. It is also clear from the plots that the eigenfunctions are vanishing at nodal points for certain values of $x \in (0, 1)$, as befits.

Figure 1: The first three eigenfunctions with corresponding energies E_1, E_2 and E_3 for an asymmetric 1D IDSQW. The wavefunctions become more oscillatory as n increases and vanish for certain values of $x \in (0, 1)$ which are called nodal points.

1.2 Dimension analysis

Dimension analysis is a useful tool for checking and verifying if the units of an equation are correct. For the 1D TISE let: T =time, M =Mass, L =Length, and E =Energy. If we revisit Eq.(1.4), with the wavefunction having units of $L^{-d/2}$, then

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{d^2}{dx^2} \psi(x) = E\psi(x) \quad (1.19)$$

⁴The uncertainty principle forbids simultaneous measurements of the position and momentum.

and our units look like

$$\frac{E^2 T^2 L^{-d/2}}{ML^2} = EL^{-d/2}. \quad (1.20)$$

This leads to

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{E^2 T^2 L^{-d/2}}{ML^2} &= \frac{\cancel{ML^2} E T^2 L^{-d/2}}{T^2 \cancel{ML^2}} \\ &= EL^{-d/2} \\ &= EL^{-1/2} \quad (d = 1) \end{aligned} \quad (1.21)$$

and clearly the units are in agreement for the one-dimensional case ($d = 1$) for Eqs.(1.20) and (1.21).⁵

1.3 The symmetric case

The symmetric potential is unlike the asymmetrical potential—Eq.(1.2)—because it is shifted by a precise distance of $L/2$ to the left and so it is defined as

$$V(x) = \begin{cases} \infty, & \text{for } x < -L/2, \\ 0, & \text{for } -L/2 < x < L/2, \\ \infty, & \text{for } x > L/2. \end{cases} \quad (1.22)$$

This shift—of distance $L/2$ —gives eigenfunctions that are either even or odd since the potential is now totally symmetric, i.e., inside the well the potential is the same for negative values of x as compared to positive values of x . The eigenfunctions may then be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_n(x) &= \sqrt{\frac{2}{L}} \sin\left(\frac{n\pi}{L}(x + L/2)\right) \\ &= \begin{cases} \sqrt{\frac{2}{L}} \cos(n\pi x/L) & (n = 1, 3, 5, \dots), \\ \sqrt{\frac{2}{L}} \sin(n\pi x/L) & (n = 2, 4, 6, \dots). \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (1.23)$$

Note that given the shift of distance $L/2$, the eigenvalues remained exactly the same as the asymmetrical case, and this should

be so because the particle’s momentum is conserved[8]. Aside from that, the cosine function is symmetric while the sine function is asymmetric which makes the eigenfunctions—Eq.(1.23)—even for odd numbers and odd for even numbers.

2 Supersymmetric quantum mechanics

Before we introduce the main idea of this section, we will elaborate on the origins of supersymmetric quantum mechanics (SUSYQM). In the early 20th century—*circa* 1912—Darboux introduced the factorization method[9]. It can be argued that without Darboux’s work, perhaps we would have no SUSYQM. Whether or not that is the case, the fact remains that SUSYQM represents a generalization of the factorization method which Darboux developed.

In 1941, Schrödinger realized that he could use the factorization method to determine the spectrum of the hydrogen atom and other potentials. It turns out that it was Dirac who factorized the harmonic oscillator and Schrödinger found its symmetry (factorization of the Schrödinger equation illustrates an underlying symmetry). Afterwards, Infeld and Hull—*circa* 1951—developed these ideas even more such that they included many more shape invariant potentials[10]. However, it wasn’t until 1981 that Edward Witten showed it was possible to construct supersymmetric partners by way of the Schrödinger equation[11]. As more excitement was being generated about SUSYQM, L.E. Gendenshtein amalgamated the ideas of solvable potentials and SUSYQM by harnessing the power of discrete reparametrization invariance[12]. Thus opening a pathway for further studies into

⁵Both the lefthand and righthand side of Eqs.(1.20–1.21) are equal to $EL^{-1/2}$.

SUSYQM.

2.1 SUSYQM basics

The bedrock of SUSYQM formalism admits:

- A Hamiltonian (\hat{H})⁶ that is hermitian;
- \hat{H} acts on Hilbert space (\mathbb{H});
- Two supercharges, Q and Q^\dagger ; and
- Q and Q^\dagger anticommute.

So therefore, the anticommuting relations become

$$\{Q, Q^\dagger\} = \hat{H} \quad (2.1)$$

and

$$\{Q, Q\} = \{Q^\dagger, Q^\dagger\} = 0. \quad (2.2)$$

The Q 's are the generators of the supersymmetry and coupled with their anticommuting properties we have the following commutator relationship:

$$[\hat{H}, Q] = [\hat{H}, Q^\dagger] = 0 \quad \hat{H} \geq 0. \quad (2.3)$$

The fact that the Q 's commute with the Hamiltonian⁷ indicates an underlying symmetry within the SUSYQM[13] framework.

Definition 2.1. A Linear operator Q is nilpotent if \exists a positive $n \in \mathbb{N} \ni Q^n = 0$. Therefore, it follows from **Def.(2.1)** that[14]

$$(Q^\dagger)^2 = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad (Q)^2 = 0.$$

We may now verify Eq.(2.3), which clearly illustrates that the Q 's generate the supersymmetry, as shown in Eq.(2.4):

$$[\hat{H}, Q] = \hat{H}Q - Q\hat{H} = Q^\dagger QQ - QQQ^\dagger = 0. \quad (2.4)$$

Now, SUSYQM requires two bosonic (A, A^\dagger) and fermionic operators (f, f^\dagger). So therefore, let the operators A, A^\dagger, f and f^\dagger be defined as,

$$A = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2m}} \frac{d}{dx} + W(x) \quad A^\dagger = \frac{-1}{\sqrt{2m}} \frac{d}{dx} + W(x)$$

⁶ \hat{H} is non-negative; its eigenvalues are positive.

⁷Note, the initial goal was to construct a supersymmetric Hamiltonian that acts on \mathbb{H} .

$$f = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad f^\dagger = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

where $W(x)$ is called the superpotential. Given A and A^\dagger are bosons, then they must adhere to the standard commutator relationship, while the two fermions f and f^\dagger anticommute, such that

$$[A, A^\dagger] = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{m}} W'(x) \quad \{f, f^\dagger\} = 1. \quad (2.5)$$

In SUSYQM, it is customary to define the supercharges as multiples of both fermionic and bosonic operators. This ensures that our Q 's anticommute, and hence [15]

$$Q = A \otimes f^\dagger = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ A & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad Q^\dagger = A^\dagger \otimes f = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & A^\dagger \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.6)$$

which satisfy Eq.(2.2). The Hamiltonian (\hat{H}) can then be expressed in matrix form as

$$\hat{H} = \{Q, Q^\dagger\} = \begin{pmatrix} A^\dagger A & 0 \\ 0 & AA^\dagger \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \hat{H}_1 & 0 \\ 0 & \hat{H}_2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.7)$$

where

$$\hat{H}_1 = \frac{-1}{2m} \frac{d^2}{dx^2} + W^2(x) - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2m}} W'(x) \quad (2.8)$$

and

$$\hat{H}_2 = \frac{-1}{2m} \frac{d^2}{dx^2} + W^2(x) + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2m}} W'(x). \quad (2.9)$$

At this point we shall let the ground state energy be zero. This implies that

$$\hat{H}_1 \psi_0(x) = \frac{-1}{2m} \frac{d^2 \psi_0(x)}{dx^2} + V_1(x) \psi_0(x) = 0, \quad (2.10)$$

and with some more algebra, we get

$$V_1(x) = \frac{1}{2m} \frac{\psi_0''(x)}{\psi_0(x)}. \quad (2.11)$$

From Eq.(2.10), the ground state wavefunction has been completely annihilated by the Hamiltonian. The fact that the ground state wavefunction vanishes, this automatically leads to a reconstruction of the potential, $V_1(x)$. Now, substituting the second and third term from Eq.(2.8) in Eq.(2.11) gives

$$\frac{1}{2m} \frac{\psi_0''(x)}{\psi_0(x)} = W^2(x) - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2m}} W'(x). \quad (2.12)$$

We must now find a solution for Eq.(2.12). The solution is obtained by recognizing that,

$$\frac{\psi_0''(x)}{\psi_0(x)} = \frac{\psi_0''(x)\psi_0(x)}{\psi_0^2(x)}, \quad (2.13)$$

then adding and subtracting $(\psi_0'(x)/\psi_0(x))^2$ on the R.H.S of Eq.(2.13). This gives,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\psi_0''(x)}{\psi_0(x)} &= \frac{\psi_0''(x)\psi_0(x)}{\psi_0^2(x)} \\ &= \frac{\psi_0''(x)\psi_0(x) - \psi_0'(x)\psi_0'(x)}{\psi_0^2(x)} + \left(\frac{\psi_0'(x)}{\psi_0(x)}\right)^2 \\ &= \left(\frac{\psi_0'(x)}{\psi_0(x)}\right)' + \left(\frac{\psi_0'(x)}{\psi_0(x)}\right)^2. \end{aligned} \quad (2.14)$$

Rearranging Eq.(2.12), followed by a direct substitution of Eq.(2.14) gives

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{\psi_0'(x)}{\psi_0(x)}\right)' + \left(\frac{\psi_0'(x)}{\psi_0(x)}\right)^2 \\ = \left(\frac{\sqrt{2m}}{\hbar} W(x)\right)^2 - \frac{\sqrt{2m}}{\hbar} W'(x) \end{aligned} \quad (2.15)$$

and our superpotential is

$$\boxed{W(x) = \frac{-\hbar}{\sqrt{2m}} \frac{\psi_0'(x)}{\psi_0(x)}}. \quad (2.16)$$

As a consequence of Eq.(2.9); due to the reordering of A^\dagger and A (which gives \hat{H}_2), we are able to introduce

$$V_2(x) = W^2(x) + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2m}} W'(x). \quad (2.17)$$

In SUSYQM V_1 and V_2 are referred to as partner potentials while \hat{H}_1 and \hat{H}_2 are the corresponding partner Hamiltonians, respectively. Nonetheless, we will concentrate on our partner Hamiltonians and develop the relationship between their eigenfunctions and eigenvalues. Henceforth, we return to Eq.(2.7) and state our first Hamiltonian as $\hat{H}_1 = AA^\dagger$ for which we shall apply to the eigenfunction $\psi_n^{(1)}(x)$ given $n > 0$. This gives

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{H}_1 \psi_n^{(1)}(x) &= AA^\dagger \psi_n^{(1)}(x) \\ &= E_n^{(1)} \psi_n^{(1)}(x), \end{aligned} \quad (2.18)$$

and similarly, the application of $\hat{H}_2 = AA^\dagger$ to $A\psi_n^{(1)}(x)$ gives

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{H}_2 (A\psi_n^{(1)}(x)) &= AA^\dagger (A\psi_n^{(1)}(x)) \\ &= E_n^{(1)} (A\psi_n^{(1)}(x)). \end{aligned} \quad (2.19)$$

Thereafter, we introduce a new eigenfunction $\psi_m^{(2)}(x)$ and prescribe the same methodology which gives us

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{H}_2 \psi_m^{(2)}(x) &= AA^\dagger (\psi_m^{(2)}(x)) \\ &= E_m^{(2)} \psi_m^{(2)}(x), \end{aligned} \quad (2.20)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{H}_1 (A^\dagger \psi_m^{(2)}(x)) &= A^\dagger AA^\dagger \psi_m^{(2)}(x) \\ &= E_m^{(2)} (A^\dagger \psi_m^{(2)}(x)). \end{aligned} \quad (2.21)$$

It is clear that \hat{H}_1 and \hat{H}_2 have eigenfunctions $\psi_n^{(1)}(x)$ and $(A\psi_n^{(1)}(x))$ respectively with eigenvalue $E_n^{(1)}$. Similarly, Eqs.(2.20, 2.21); the partner Hamiltonians have eigenfunctions $(A^\dagger \psi_m^{(2)}(x))$ and $\psi_m^{(2)}(x)$ respectively with eigenvalue $E_m^{(2)}$. This means that the spectra of \hat{H}_1 and \hat{H}_2 are degenerate except for the ground state energy of \hat{H}_2 which is zero. The reason for the non-degenerate

ground state has to do with the fact that $\psi_0^{(1)}(x)$ is node free.

In the previous paragraph we specified that for $n > 0$ then $\psi_n^{(1)}(x)$ is valid, without a thorough explanation of why that is the case. Nonetheless, for $n = 0$

$$\hat{H}_2(A\psi_0^{(1)}(x)) = AA^\dagger(A\psi_0^{(1)}(x)) = 0. \quad (2.22)$$

This implies that

$$E_0^1 = 0, \quad (2.23)$$

and \hat{H}_2 has a ground state energy of zero. In addition to that, we can construct relationships between the eigenfunctions and eigenvalues with respect to their partner Hamiltonians. So therefore, if we let $\psi_n^{(2)}(x) \propto A\psi_{n+1}^{(1)}(x)$ and N be a normalization constant, then

$$\psi_n^{(2)}(x) = NA\psi_{n+1}^{(1)}(x) \quad (2.24)$$

and so

$$\begin{aligned} \underbrace{\langle \psi_n^{(2)}(x) | \psi_n^{(2)}(x) \rangle}_{=1} &= N^2 \langle \psi_{n+1}^{(1)}(x) | A^\dagger A | \psi_{n+1}^{(1)}(x) \rangle \\ &= N^2 \langle \psi_{n+1}^{(1)}(x) | \hat{H}_1 | \psi_{n+1}^{(1)}(x) \rangle \\ &= N^2 \langle \psi_{n+1}^{(1)}(x) | E_{n+1}^{(1)} | \psi_{n+1}^{(1)}(x) \rangle \\ &= N^2 E_{n+1}^{(1)} \underbrace{\langle \psi_{n+1}^{(1)}(x) | \psi_{n+1}^{(1)}(x) \rangle}_{=1} \\ &= N^2 E_{n+1}^{(1)}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.25)$$

Hence

$$\psi_n^{(2)}(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{E_{n+1}^{(1)}}} A\psi_{n+1}^{(1)}(x) \quad (2.26)$$

and similarly

$$\psi_{n+1}^{(1)}(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{E_n^{(2)}}} A^\dagger \psi_n^{(2)}(x). \quad (2.27)$$

We should also mention that

$$E_n^{(2)} = E_{n+1}^{(1)} \quad (2.28)$$

or in other words, the second eigenvalue of \hat{H}_1 is equal to the first eigenvalue of \hat{H}_2 . This is in accordance with an important implication of SUSYQM which guarantees that if the complete spectrum of \hat{H}_1 is known then we can automatically determine the complete spectrum of \hat{H}_2 [9].

2.2 Exactly solvable potential

We return to Subsection (1.1) and revisit the 1D IDSQW to determine its partner potential. This is achieved by first subtracting E_0 from E_n which gives ($n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$)

$$\begin{aligned} E_n^{(1)} &= E_n - E_0 \\ &= \frac{(n+1)^2 \pi^2 \hbar^2}{2mL^2} - \frac{\pi^2 \hbar^2}{2mL^2} = n(n+2) \frac{\pi^2 \hbar^2}{2mL^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.29)$$

So $E_n^{(1)}$ is the energy that corresponds to \hat{H}_1 and is accompanied by its normalized wavefunction

$$\psi_n^{(1)}(x) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{L}} \sin \frac{(n+1)\pi x}{L} \quad (x \in (0, L)). \quad (2.30)$$

Now using Eq.(2.16), the superpotential becomes

$$W(x) = \frac{-\hbar}{\sqrt{2m}} \frac{\psi_0'(x)}{\psi_0(x)} = -\frac{\hbar\pi}{\sqrt{2mL}} \cot(\pi x/L) \quad (2.31)$$

where

$$\psi_0^{(1)}(x) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{L}} \sin \frac{\pi x}{L}. \quad (2.32)$$

The superpotential is then substituted in Eq.(2.17) and hence the partner potential (V_2) is given by

$$\begin{aligned} V_2(x) &= W^2(x) + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2m}} W'(x) \\ &= \frac{\pi^2 \hbar^2}{2mL^2} (2 \csc^2(\pi x/L) - 1). \end{aligned} \quad (2.33)$$

In order to determine the eigenfunctions of the second partner Hamiltonian, we re-introduce the operator A and by direct application of the said operator to $\psi_n^{(2)}(x)$ we can write the first few wavefunctions (for \hat{H}_2) as

$$\begin{aligned}\psi_0^{(2)}(x) &= \frac{A\psi_1^{(1)}(x)}{\sqrt{E_1^{(1)}}} \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{3\pi^2\hbar^2/2mL^2}} \sqrt{\frac{2}{L}} \left(\frac{\hbar}{\sqrt{2m}} \frac{d}{dx} - \frac{\hbar}{\sqrt{2m}} \frac{\pi}{L} \cot(\pi x/L) \right) \sin(2\pi x/L) \\ &= -2\sqrt{\frac{2}{3L}} \sin^2(\pi x/L), \quad (2.34)\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}\psi_1^{(2)}(x) &= \frac{A\psi_2^{(1)}(x)}{\sqrt{E_2^{(1)}}} \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{8\pi^2\hbar^2/2mL^2}} \sqrt{\frac{2}{L}} \left(\frac{\hbar}{\sqrt{2m}} \frac{d}{dx} - \frac{\hbar}{\sqrt{2m}} \frac{\pi}{L} \cot(\pi x/L) \right) \sin(3\pi x/L) \\ &= -\frac{2}{\sqrt{L}} \sin(\pi x/L) \sin(2\pi x/L). \quad (2.35)\end{aligned}$$

An outstanding feature of SUSYQM displayed in the 1D IDSQW is that, irrespective of having acquired two dissimilar partner potentials, the spectra of \hat{H}_1 and \hat{H}_2 are completely degenerate (except for the ground state). So if the entire spectrum of \hat{H}_1 is known, we automatically know the complete spectrum of \hat{H}_2 . In addition, if we revisit Eq.(1.10) and compare it to Eq.(2.30) it should be clear that n is shifted to $n+1$. This ensures that the infinite potential well has a ground state eigenfunction while its partner potential $V_2(x)$ (the trigonometric Pöschl-Teller potential) does not. Also, even though a shift from $n \rightarrow n+1$ was necessary, the physics of this kind of problem remains in-

variant. Furthermore, because of the extra ground state eigenfunction belonging to \hat{H}_1 , our system has unbroken supersymmetry given by

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta &= Tr(-1)^{N_F} = n_B - n_F \neq 0 \\ &\{\text{Unbroken Supersymmetry}\}. \quad (2.36)\end{aligned}$$

Now, in the absence of the extra ground state eigenfunction we have

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta &= Tr(-1)^{N_F} = n_B - n_F = 0 \\ &\{\text{Broken Supersymmetry}\}, \quad (2.37)\end{aligned}$$

where Δ is the so-called *Witten index*[16], N_F is the fermion number (N.B., one fermion allowed in one state only which admits to the Pauli exclusion principle), n_B , and n_F are the possible zero energy ground states, respectively.

3 q -Calculus

Quantum calculus is simply calculus done without the notion of limits as compared to normal calculus. Its origins can be traced to the 1740s when Swiss mathematician, Leonhard Euler was working on the theory of partitions. The work on q -calculus continued to progress under C.F. Gauß-with the invention of the hypergeometric series in 1812-and later led to the discovery of the q -binomial coefficient[17].

Definition 3.1. The q -integer with parameter $q \in (0, 1)$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$ is given by:

$$[n]_q = \begin{cases} \frac{1-q^n}{1-q}, & \text{if } q \neq 1 \\ n, & \text{if } q = 1 \end{cases}$$

for $q \in \mathbb{R}$.

There exist an alternative to **Def.(3.1)** and it is invariant under the interchange of $q \rightarrow \frac{1}{q}$ with $[n]_q = [n]_{\frac{1}{q}}$. This is called the symmetrized form of the q -integer and is given by

$$[n]_{\frac{1}{q}} = q^{\frac{1}{2}(n-1)} + q^{\frac{1}{2}(n-3)} + \dots q^{-\frac{1}{2}(n-1)}. \quad (3.1)$$

Another important fact about this alternate definition of the q -integer is that it forms an additive group under the addition law such that:

Lemma 3.1. Given $m, n \in \mathbb{Z}$ then

$$[m]_q \oplus [n]_q = q^{-\frac{n}{2}}[m]_q + q^{\frac{m}{2}}[n]_q,$$

and the group $\{\mathbb{Z}, +\}$ is isomorphic to $\{[n]_q, \oplus\}$ or in other words

$$\{\mathbb{Z}, +\} \cong \{[n]_q, \oplus\} | n \in \mathbb{Z}.$$

The q -integer can be generalized to the so-called q -number $[x]_q$ where $x \in \mathbb{R}$ and

$$[x]_q = \frac{q^{\frac{x}{2}} - q^{-\frac{x}{2}}}{q^{\frac{1}{2}} - q^{-\frac{1}{2}}}, \quad (3.2)$$

and since

$$[x \oplus y]_q = q^{\frac{x}{2}}[y]_q + q^{-\frac{y}{2}}[x]_q = q^{-\frac{x}{2}}[y]_q + q^{\frac{y}{2}}[x]_q, \quad (3.3)$$

under the addition law, the group $\{\mathbb{R}, +\}$ is isomorphic to $\{[x]_q, \oplus\}$, i.e.,

$$\{\mathbb{R}, +\} \cong \{[x]_q, \oplus\} | x \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (3.4)$$

Definition 3.2. The additive inverse with parameter $q \in (0, 1)$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$ is given by

$$[n]_q + [-n]_q = 0$$

for $q \in \mathbb{R}$.

Definition 3.3. The q -factorial with parameter $q \in (0, 1)$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$ is given by

$$[n]_q! = \begin{cases} [n]_q[n-1]_q \dots [1]_q, & n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, \\ 1, & n = 0 \end{cases}$$

for $q \in \mathbb{R}$ ⁸.

Definition 3.4. The q -exponential function with $q \in (0, 1)$ -is defined by

$$e_q(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{[n]_q!}.$$

⁸As q approaches 1 the quantum definitions regain their classical definitions.

Definition 3.5. The q -trigonometric functions—with $q \in (0, 1)$ —are defined by

$$\begin{aligned} \sin_q x &= \frac{e_q^{ix} - e_q^{-ix}}{2i}, & \cos_q x &= \frac{e_q^{ix} + e_q^{-ix}}{2} \\ \text{Sin}_q x &= \frac{E_q^{ix} - E_q^{-ix}}{2i}, & \text{Cos}_q x &= \frac{E_q^{ix} + E_q^{-ix}}{2} \end{aligned}$$

where $\text{Sin}_q x = \sin_{1/q} x$, $\text{Cos}_q x = \cos_{1/q} x$, and $E_q(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} q^{n(n-1)/2} \frac{x^n}{[n]_q!}$.

A binomial is simply a polynomial with two terms which are called monomials. Binomials can be expanded to produced what is known as a binomial series or expansion—which is a collection of a number of algebraic terms. The prefactors of each term are called binomial coefficients and are defined as $C(n, k)$. $C(n, k)$ should be interpreted as n choose k or the number of possible ways to choose k elements from n elements. In quantum calculus we have the so-called q -binomial coefficients with nonnegative integers n and j as shown in Eqs.(3.5, 3.6). Since these equations are just the q -analogs of the classical form, it is immediately recognized that in the limit as $q \rightarrow 1$ the ordinary binomial coefficients are recovered.

From **Def.(3.3)**, and the fact that there exist two q -Pascal rules—Eqs.(3.5, 3.6)—or the so-called recurrence relations (for $1 \leq j \leq n-1$), we may write the rules as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{[n]_q!}{[j]_q![n-j]_q!} &= \frac{[n-1]_q!}{[j-1]_q![n-j]_q!} \\ &+ q^j \frac{[n-1]_q!}{[j]_q![n-1-j]_q!}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.5)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{[n]_q!}{[j]_q![n-j]_q!} &= q^{n-j} \frac{[n-1]_q!}{[j-1]_q![n-j]_q!} \\ &+ \frac{[n-1]_q!}{[j]_q![n-1-j]_q!}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.6)$$

Proof. Now suppose x and y are non-commuting coordinates in the *quantum plane*⁹ and the commutation relations

$$\boxed{xy = qyx} \quad (3.7)$$

are satisfied. Then, following from **Def.(3.1–3.3)**, a non-commutative binomial formula of the form

$$\begin{aligned} (x+y)^{n+1} &= (x+y)^n(x+y) \\ &= \left(\sum_{j=0}^n \frac{[n]_q!}{[j]_q![n-j]_q!} x^j y^{n-j} \right) (x+y) \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^n \frac{[n]_q!}{[j]_q![n-j]_q!} x^j y^{n-j} x \\ &\quad + \sum_{j=0}^n \frac{[n]_q!}{[j]_q![n-j]_q!} x^j y^{n-j+1} \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^n \frac{[n]_q!}{[j]_q![n-j]_q!} x^j [q^{n-j} x y^{n-j}] \\ &\quad + \sum_{j=0}^n \frac{[n]_q!}{[j]_q![n-j]_q!} x^j y^{n-j+1} \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^{n+1} q^{n-j+1} \frac{[n]_q!}{[j-1]_q![n-j+1]_q!} x^j y^{n-j+1} \\ &\quad + \sum_{j=0}^n \frac{[n]_q!}{[j]_q![n-j]_q!} x^j y^{n-j+1} \\ &= \lambda + \sum_{j=1}^n q^{n-j+1} \frac{[n]_q!}{[j-1]_q![n-j+1]_q!} x^j y^{n-j+1} \\ &\quad + \sum_{j=1}^n q^{n-j+1} \frac{[n]_q!}{[j]_q![n-j]_q!} x^j y^{n-j+1} + \zeta \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^{n+1} \frac{[n+1]_q!}{[j]_q![n+1-j]_q!} x^j y^{n+1-j} \quad (3.8) \end{aligned}$$

is shown to be true using mathematical induction and the q -Pascal rules, where $\lambda = y^{n+1}$ and $\zeta = x^{n+1}$. \square

⁹The quantum plane is essentially a two-dimensional plane.

¹⁰Quantum differentials possess a symmetry preserving property.

3.1 The q -derivative

Definition 3.6. Suppose $f(x)$ is a function that is differentiable, continuous and $f'(0)$ exist, then the q -derivative (denoted by D_q) of the function $f(x)$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} (D_q f)(x) &= \frac{f(x) - f(qx)}{(1-q)x} \\ &= \frac{d_q f(x)}{d_q x}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.9)$$

for $x \neq 0$.

The beauty and simplicity of such a differential lies with the fact that unlike the classical derivative which is the ratio of two infinitesimals, the q -differential is simply the ratio of $d_q f(x)$ to that of $d_q x$. Another important fact related to quantum differentials is their ability to preserve the symmetry of the product of two functions unlike classical differentials¹⁰.

Note, in the early 20th century the q -derivative presented hereto was dubbed the *Jackson q -derivative*. It was Jackson and Euler who were credited with the development of this more generalized differential operator. Anyhow, notice that in the limit $q \rightarrow 1$ the classical derivative is recovered—this is true only if $f(x)$ is differentiable at x —and hence

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} (D_q f)(x) = \frac{df(x)}{dx}. \quad (3.10)$$

An example of applying the q -derivative on the function $f(x) = x^\gamma$, with $\gamma \in \mathbb{C}$ gives

$$D_q(x^\gamma) = \frac{x^\gamma - (qx)^\gamma}{(1-q)x} = \frac{x^\gamma(1-q^\gamma)}{(1-q)x}. \quad (3.11)$$

In addition, using **Def.(3.6)**, and the fact that D_q is a linear operator—for constants α and β we have the linearity property

$$D_q\{\alpha f(x) + \beta g(x)\} = \alpha D_q\{f(x)\} + \beta D_q\{g(x)\}. \quad (3.12)$$

Furthermore, for arbitrary functions $f(x)$ and $g(x)$ we may write the product rule as

$$\begin{aligned}
D_q\{f(x)g(x)\} &= \\
& \frac{f(qx)g(qx) - f(x)g(x)}{(q-1)x} \\
&= \frac{f(qx)g(qx) - f(qx)g(x)}{(q-1)x} \\
& \quad + \frac{f(qx)g(x) - f(x)g(x)}{(q-1)x} \\
&= \frac{f(qx)(g(qx) - g(x))}{(q-1)x} \\
& \quad + \frac{(f(qx) - f(x))g(x)}{(q-1)x} \\
&= f(qx)D_qg(x) \\
& \quad + D_qf(x)g(x). \quad (3.13)
\end{aligned}$$

Also, the generalized quotient rule for $f(x)$ and $g(x)$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
D_q\left\{\frac{f(x)}{g(x)}\right\} &= \\
&= \frac{1}{(q-1)x} \left\{ \frac{f(qx)}{g(qx)} - \frac{f(x)}{g(qx)} \right\} \\
& \quad + \frac{1}{(q-1)x} \left\{ \frac{f(x)}{g(qx)} - \frac{f(x)}{g(x)} \right\} \\
&= \frac{1}{g(qx)} \left\{ \frac{f(qx) - f(x)}{(q-1)x} \right\} \\
& \quad + \frac{1}{(q-1)x} \left\{ \frac{f(x)g(x) - f(x)g(qx)}{g(qx)g(x)} \right\} \\
&= \frac{1}{g(qx)} D_qf(x) \\
& \quad + \frac{f(x)}{g(qx)g(x)} \left\{ \frac{g(x) - g(qx)}{(q-1)x} \right\} \\
&= \frac{g(x)D_qf(x) - f(x)D_qg(x)}{g(qx)g(x)}, \quad (3.14)
\end{aligned}$$

At this stage, it appears that the logical thing to do is explore the chain rule for an arbitrary function—Does a generalized chain rule exist for $f(u(x))$ given Eq.(3.15)? It turns out that no such rule exist¹¹ but that does not mean we cannot choose an appropriate function that satisfies the chain rule. For example, if we have $f(u(x)) = f(\alpha x^\beta)$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
D_q\{f(u(x))\} &= \\
D_q\{f(\alpha x^\beta)\} &= \frac{f(\alpha q^\beta x^\beta) - f(\alpha x^\beta)}{(q-1)x} \\
&= \frac{f(\alpha q^\beta x^\beta) - f(\alpha x^\beta)}{\alpha q^\beta x^\beta - \alpha x^\beta} \times \frac{\alpha q^\beta x^\beta - \alpha x^\beta}{(q-1)x} \\
&= (D_{q^\beta}f)(u(x))D_q(u(x)). \quad (3.15)
\end{aligned}$$

3.2 The q -integral

Suppose we have a function $f(x)$, then its antiderivative is defined as $F(x)' = f(x)$, $\forall x$ in the set of departure of f . In classical calculus the function $f(x)$ can have multiple antiderivatives and therefore the antiderivative is not unique. For example, if $F(x) = x^4$, $\gamma(x) = x^4 - 25$, and $\Gamma(x) = x^4 + 10$, then $\Gamma(x)' = \gamma(x)' = F(x)' = f(x) = 4x^3$. Therefore it should be clear that the antiderivative of a function is not unique up to a constant and it turns out that the q -analog does not have a unique antiderivative.

Definition 3.7. A q -antiderivative¹² of a function is defined as $D_qF(x) = f(x)$ where the function $F(x)$ is called the q -antiderivative of $f(x)$ [18], hence

$$\int f(x)d_qx. \quad (3.16)$$

¹¹In the current literature no generalized chain rule has been developed.

¹²The q -antiderivative is not unique up to a constant.

¹³The Jackson integral is an infinite Riemann sum.

The *Jackson integral*¹³ of a function $f(x)$ is given by

$$\int f(x)d_q x = (1-q)x \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} q^j f(q^j x), \quad (3.17)$$

and this leads to a more generalized definition[18] of the said integral which is written as

$$\begin{aligned} \int f(x)D_q g(x)d_q x &= \\ (1-q)x \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} q^j f(q^j x)D_q g(q^j x) & \\ = (1-q)x \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} q^j f(q^j x) \frac{g(q^j x) - g(q^{j+1} x)}{(1-q)q^j x}. & \end{aligned} \quad (3.18)$$

Remark 1. *The function $f(x)$ has at most one q -antiderivative; a testament to its uniqueness $\forall q \in (0, 1)$ up to a constant.*

Theorem 3.2. (Fundamental theorem of q -calculus) If $\Gamma(x)$ is an antiderivative of $\lambda(x)$ and $\Gamma(x)$ is continuous at $x = 0$ [18], then

$$\int_x^y \lambda(x)d_q x = \Gamma(x) - \Gamma(y) \quad (0 \leq x < y \leq \infty). \quad (3.19)$$

The fundamental theorem of q -calculus can then be applied to the interval $[x, y]$, and we may write

$$\begin{aligned} \int_x^y \lambda(x)d_q x &= \int_0^y \lambda(x)d_q x - \int_0^x \lambda(x)d_q x \\ &= \Gamma(y) - \Gamma(x). \end{aligned} \quad (3.20)$$

Additionally, the q -analog of integration by parts or q -integration by parts is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \int_x^y \lambda(x)d_q \gamma(x) &= \lambda(y)\gamma(y) - \lambda(x)\gamma(x) \\ &\quad - \int_x^y \gamma(qx)d_q \lambda(x), \end{aligned} \quad (3.21)$$

and the improper q -integral is defined as

$$\int_0^{\infty} \lambda(x)d_q x = \sum_{j=-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{q^{j+1}}^{q^j} \lambda(x)d_q x \quad q \in (0, 1) \quad (3.22)$$

or

$$\int_0^{\infty} \lambda(x)d_q x = \sum_{j=-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{q^j}^{q^{j+1}} \lambda(x)d_q x \quad (q > 1). \quad (3.23)$$

Remark 2. *The definite classical integral is different from its quantum counterpart due to the definition of the definite q -integral. On the interval $[a, b]$ —when integrating—note that the Jackson integral vanishes at $x = 0$.*

4 q -Quantum mechanics

Any operator \hat{A} with a real expectation value in quantum mechanics is called a hermitian operator. All hermitian operators admit to the relationship $\hat{A} = \hat{A}^\dagger$ where \dagger represents the hermitian conjugate of the operator \hat{A} . Hermitian operators are associated with the physical measurements of the system and it might be the case that a measurement is required on a large number of identical systems[19]. If we denote each identical system as, $\hat{A}_1, \hat{A}_2, \hat{A}_3, \hat{A}_4, \dots, \hat{A}_n$ then the average value—*expectation value*—of our system is

$$\langle \hat{A} \rangle = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \hat{A}_n \quad (N \neq 0). \quad (4.1)$$

Just as quantum mechanics requires that operators are subject to real expectation values, in q -quantum mechanics operators must be q -hermitian. If this were not the case, the momentum operator—in q -quantum mechanics—would not be q -hermitian or even q -skew hermitian. Hence, the energy operator would not be q -hermitian.

4.1 q -Hermitian operator

In order to satisfy the requirement that our energy operator be q -hermitian, we introduce the dilation operator which is denoted by \hat{Z} . We shall then conveniently choose an arbitrary test function— $\lambda(x)$ —and directly apply the dialtion operator, which gives

$$\hat{Z}\lambda(x) = \lambda(qx). \quad (4.2)$$

If $\lambda(x) = x^p$, then

$$\hat{Z}\lambda(x) = \hat{Z}x^p = q^p x^p, \quad (4.3)$$

where $q^p = e^{p \ln q}$. Expanding Eq.(4.3) in a taylor series leads to

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{Z}\lambda(x) = & \left(1 + \frac{p \ln(q)}{1!} + \frac{(p \ln(q))^2}{2!} \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{(p \ln(q))^3}{3!} + \frac{(p \ln(q))^4}{4!} + \dots + \right) x^p \end{aligned} \quad (4.4)$$

and replacing p by $x\partial_x$ we get a final result of

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{Z}\lambda(x) = & \left(1 + \frac{x\partial_x \ln(q)}{1!} + \frac{(x\partial_x \ln(q))^2}{2!} \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{(x\partial_x \ln(q))^3}{3!} + \frac{(x\partial_x \ln(q))^4}{4!} + \dots + \right) x^p, \end{aligned} \quad (4.5)$$

which is just equivalent to Eq.(4.3), so

$$\boxed{\hat{Z} = q^{x\partial_x}}. \quad (4.6)$$

A q -hermitian operator \hat{A}_q must have real eigenvalues and so for an arbitrary q -eigenfunction $\chi_{q,m}(x)$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \int \chi_{q,m}^*(x) \hat{A}_q \chi_{q,n}(x) d(qx) \\ & = \int (\hat{A}_q \chi_{q,m}(x))^* \chi_{q,n} d(qx) \end{aligned} \quad (4.7)$$

which implies that,

$$\begin{aligned} & \int \chi_{q,m}^*(x) \xi_m \chi_{q,n}(x) - \xi_n^* \chi_{q,m}^*(x) \chi_{q,n}(x) d(qx) \\ & = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4.8)$$

and therefore

$$(\xi_m - \xi_n^*) \int \chi_{q,m}(x) \chi_{q,n}(x) d(qx) = 0. \quad (4.9)$$

Now for $m = n$ the

$$\int \chi_{q,m}(x) \chi_{q,n}(x) d(qx) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad (\xi_m = \xi_n^*), \quad (4.10)$$

hence the eigenvalues of a q -hermitian operator are real.

The dilation operator defined as \hat{Z} in Eq.(4.6) is necessary in the development of a correct q -hermitian operator. The product of the q -difference equation with \hat{Z} gives a new definition of a q -hermitian operator which is the q -analog of the momentum operator in non-relativistic quantum mechanics, and is given by

$$D_{q,x} D_{q,x} \hat{Z} = D_{q,x}^2 \hat{Z}. \quad (4.11)$$

Provided that the q -eigenfunctions $\chi_{q,m}^*(x)$ and $\chi_{q,n}(x)$ are q -square integrable, i.e.,

$$\int \chi_{q,m}^*(x) \chi_{q,n}(x) d(qx) < \infty, \quad (4.12)$$

then—as in quantum mechanics—as the q -eigenfunctions approach $\pm\infty$ we can show using q -integration by parts—Eq.(3.20)—that Eq.(4.12) is q -hermitian. Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} & \int \chi_{q,m}^*(x) D_{q,x}^2 \hat{Z} \chi_{q,n}(x) d(qx) = \\ & \int \chi_{q,m}^*(x) D_{q,x} (D_{q,x} \hat{Z} \chi_{q,n}(x)) d(qx) \\ & = [\chi_{q,m}^*(x) D_{q,x} \chi_{q,n}(q^{-1}x)]_{-\infty}^{\infty} - \\ & \int D_{q,x} \chi_{q,m}^*(x) q^{1/2} D_{q,x} \chi_{q,n}(x) d(qx) \\ & = -q^{1/2} \int D_{q,x} \chi_{q,m}^*(x) D_{q,x} \chi_{q,n}(x) d(qx) \\ & = \int (D_{q,x}^2 \hat{Z} \chi_{q,m}(x))^* \chi_{q,n}(x) d(qx). \end{aligned} \quad (4.13)$$

4.2 q -Orthogonality

The set $\mathbf{L}^2[a, b]$ has a linear structure as compared to the n -dimensional complex space \mathbb{C}^n for all square-integrable functions. It is known or—the space $\mathbf{L}^2[0, L]$ —referred to as "Hilbert space", and will be denoted by the letter \mathbb{H} hereinafter. For any two functions $\chi_{q,m}(x), \chi_{q,n}(x) \in \mathbb{H}$ which are q -square-integrable, linear combinations of $a\chi_{q,m}(x) + b\chi_{q,n}(x)$ are also q -square-integrable and therefore live in the space \mathbb{H} . If we include the difference between the two aforementioned functions as $d(\chi_{q,m}(x), \chi_{q,n}(x)) = \|\chi_{q,m}(x) - \chi_{q,n}(x)\|$, then we have an induced metric which is a complete normed spaced or q -Banach space.

The q -eigenvectors corresponding to different eigenvalues in q -quantum mechanics are q -orthogonal. Let \hat{A}_q be a q -hermitian operator that lives q -Banach space, then

$$\hat{A}_q |\chi_{q,n}(x)\rangle = \xi_n |\chi_{q,n}(x)\rangle \quad (4.14)$$

$$\langle \chi_{q,m}(x) | \hat{A}_q | \chi_{q,n}(x) \rangle = \xi_n \langle \chi_{q,m}(x) | \chi_{q,n}(x) \rangle \quad (4.15)$$

and for the adjoint operator

$$\langle \chi_{q,m}(x) | \hat{A}_q^\dagger = \xi_m^* \langle \chi_{q,m}(x) | \quad (4.16)$$

$$\langle \chi_{q,m}(x) | \hat{A}_q^\dagger | \chi_{q,n}(x) \rangle = \xi_m^* \langle \chi_{q,m}(x) | \chi_{q,n}(x) \rangle \quad (4.17)$$

therefore

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle \chi_{q,m}(x) | \hat{A}_q | \chi_{q,n}(x) \rangle - \langle \chi_{q,m}(x) | \hat{A}_q^\dagger | \chi_{q,n}(x) \rangle \\ & = (\xi_n - \xi_m^*) \langle \chi_{q,m}(x) | \chi_{q,n}(x) \rangle. \end{aligned} \quad (4.18)$$

Of course for $m \neq n$, $\xi_m^* \neq \xi_n$ and $\langle \chi_{q,m}(x) | \chi_{q,n}(x) \rangle = 0$.

4.3 1D q -Schrödinger equation

Revisiting Subsection (1.1), we make use of Eq.(1.2) but this time our potential

will be called the q -infinite square well potential— $V_q(x)$ —and is defined as

$$V_q(x) = \begin{cases} \infty, & \text{for } x < 0, \\ [0]_q, & \text{for } 0 < x < L, \\ \infty, & \text{for } x > L. \end{cases} \quad (4.19)$$

Since the potential must vanish at the boundaries and we have a q -hermitian operator which is the analog of the momentum operator; the Hamiltonian is given by

$$\hat{H}_q = \frac{-\hbar^2}{2m} D_{q,x}^2 \hat{Z} + V_q(x), \quad (4.20)$$

and the q -Schrödinger equation is written as

$$\hat{H}_q \psi_q(x) = \epsilon_q \psi_q(x). \quad (4.21)$$

Hence,

$$\left\{ \frac{-\hbar^2}{2m} D_{q,x}^2 \hat{Z} + [0]_q \right\} \psi_q(x) - \epsilon_q \psi_q(x) = 0, \quad (4.22)$$

which ultimately leads to

$$\left\{ D_{q,x}^2 \hat{Z} + \frac{2m\epsilon_q}{\hbar^2} \right\} \psi_q(x) = 0. \quad (4.23)$$

The q -eigenvalues and corresponding q -eigenfunctions are given by

$$\epsilon_q = \frac{k_q^2 \hbar^2}{2m}, \quad (4.24)$$

and

$$\psi_q(x) = B_q E_q(ikx) \quad (4.25)$$

where B_q is the q -normalization constant determined from[20]

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \psi_q^*(x) \psi_q(x) d(qx) = 1. \quad (4.26)$$

5 Fractional calculus

The question of whether or not a differential operator of the form $\frac{d^n y}{dx^n}$ and of order n , where $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ could be expressed in fractional order was posed to Leibniz nearly 320 years ago[21]. Bernoulli and L'Hopital were curious about noninteger representations of the differential operator and because of the preceding fact we have the genesis of fractional calculus. However, to simplify the former statement even more, fractional calculus should be thought of as a promotion of the integer order n to an arbitrary order α where $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}$ with respect to the differential operator[22–24]. That is, $\frac{d^n}{dx^n} \rightarrow \frac{d^\alpha}{dx^\alpha}$.

5.1 The fractional Leibniz rule

To elucidate more on the nature of fractional calculus, we employ the use of the fractional derivative and the Leibniz product rule. Suppose we are given two functions Υ and Φ , then the un-fractionalized Leibniz product rule is given by

$$\frac{d}{dx}(\Upsilon\Phi) = \left\{\frac{d}{dx}\Upsilon\right\}\Phi + \Upsilon\left\{\frac{d}{dx}\Phi\right\}. \quad (5.1)$$

But it turns out that the fractionalization of Eq.(5.1) is invalid. Nevertheless, we are still able to develop a workable Leibniz product rule for larger values of n , i.e.,

$$\frac{d}{dx}(\Upsilon\Phi) = \left\{\frac{d}{dx}\Upsilon\right\}\Phi + \Upsilon\left\{\frac{d}{dx}\Phi\right\}, \quad (5.2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2}{dx^2}(\Upsilon\Phi) &= \left\{\frac{d^2}{dx^2}\Upsilon\right\}\Phi + 2\left\{\frac{d}{dx}\Upsilon\right\}\left\{\frac{d}{dx}\Phi\right\} \\ &\quad + \Upsilon\left\{\frac{d^2}{dx^2}\Phi\right\} \end{aligned} \quad (5.3)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^3}{dx^3}(\Upsilon\Phi) &= \left\{\frac{d^3}{dx^3}\Upsilon\right\}\Phi + 3\left\{\frac{d^2}{dx^2}\Upsilon\right\}\left\{\frac{d}{dx}\Phi\right\} \\ &\quad + 3\left\{\frac{d}{dx}\Upsilon\right\}\left\{\frac{d^2}{dx^2}\Phi\right\} + \Upsilon\left\{\frac{d^3}{dx^3}\Phi\right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (5.4)$$

Now if we let $\partial_x^\alpha = \frac{d^\alpha}{dx^\alpha}$; following from Eqs.(5.1–5.4) we have a general rule for higher orders of $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Since the derivation of this rule is valid $\forall n \in \mathbb{N}$ we can then write

$$\partial_x^n(\Upsilon\Phi) = \sum_{i=0}^n \binom{n}{i} \{\partial_x^{n-i}\Upsilon\}\{\partial_x^i\Phi\}. \quad (5.5)$$

The next step just requires a promotion of n to $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}$ of our generalized rule—Eq.(5.5)—which are the basic underlying ideas of fractional calculus. And consequently, we arrive at the fractional Leibniz product rule

$$\partial_x^\alpha(\Upsilon\Phi) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \binom{\alpha}{\vartheta+i} \{\partial_x^{\alpha-\vartheta-i}\Upsilon\}\{\partial_x^{i+\vartheta}\Phi\}, \quad (5.6)$$

for which the term ϑ can be selected randomly.

5.2 1D fractional Schrödinger equation

As a starting point for the development of the free fractional Schrödinger equation[25], we begin with the classical Hamiltonian for a system of N particles that is dependent on position and momentum (x^i, P_i) . The terms in parenthesis are called canonical conjugate pairs and are the building blocks of our classical Hamiltonian,

$$H_1 = \sum_{i=1}^{3N} \frac{P_i^2}{2m} + V(x^1, \dots, x^i, \dots, x^{3N}). \quad (5.7)$$

Now if we promote $x^i \rightarrow \hat{X}^i$ and $P_i \rightarrow \hat{P}_i$, i.e., the classical canonical conjugate pairs to quantum mechanical observables, then the new quantized fractional Hamiltonian may be written as

$$H^\alpha = \sum_{i=1}^{3N} \frac{\hat{P}_i^2}{2m} + V(\hat{X}^1, \dots, \hat{X}^i, \dots, \hat{X}^{3N}). \quad (5.8)$$

If the potential is zero, we have a case for which the 1D fractional Schrödinger equation is given by

$$H_{free}^{\alpha}\psi = -\frac{1}{2}mc^2 \left(\frac{\hbar}{mc}\right)^{2\alpha} \hat{D}^{\alpha} \hat{D}^{\alpha}\psi = E\psi. \quad (5.9)$$

Before we move on to the symmetric case for the infinite potential we should mention that there exist no exact analytic solution for the fractional infinite potential well. This is so because the definitions of the fractional derivatives in the case of the Riemann and Caputo, Liouville, Fourier, and Riesz fractional derivative[26, 27] are defined differently. In other words, the fractional derivatives that may be utilized to find solutions to the fractional infinite potential well are not unique.

Fractional derivatives are nonlocal—in some cases they can be localized[28]—by definition, since imbedded in their definitions are integrals which are associated with many different past histories. For convenience and simplicity we will use the fractional Fourier derivative in our discussion of the infinite potential well for $\alpha \approx 1$ while considering nonlocality and memory effects. Memory effects of the fractionalized derivative refers to the instantaneous rate of change and its dependency on past states. While nonlocality is directly linked to a fixed function called the kernel—embedded in the integral of the fractional derivative—but requires varying forms of the said kernel to match varying past histories to depict their memory effects. Note, for $\alpha \rightarrow 1$ most of the past histories are annihilated and the system evolves through the present state[29].

The free fractional Schrödinger equation—Eq.(5.9)—must satisfy the boundary conditions for the symmetric case discussed in Subsection (1.3), i.e.,

$$\psi(-L/2) = \psi(L/2). \quad (5.10)$$

We should emphasize again that we are using the fractional Fourier derivative for $\alpha \approx 1$. The solutions—approximate solutions—of the free fractional Schrödinger equation based on Fourier’s fractional derivative for a 1D IS-DQW are

$$\psi(\alpha \approx 1, x) = \begin{cases} {}_F \cos(\alpha, x/x_0(n, \alpha)) & n = 0, 2, 4, \dots \\ {}_F \sin(\alpha, x/x_0(n, \alpha)) & n = 1, 3, 5, \dots, \end{cases} \quad (5.11)$$

where the zeroes are defined as

$${}_F x_0(n, \alpha) = \frac{(n+1)\pi}{\sin(\pi/L)} \frac{\pi}{2}. \quad (5.12)$$

The Fourier energy eigenvalues for the 1D symmetric case can then be written as

$$E(\alpha \approx 1, n) = \frac{1}{2}mc^2 \left(\frac{\hbar}{mc}\right)^{2\alpha} \left(\frac{\pi}{2\sin(\pi/L)}\right)^{2\alpha} (n+1)^{2\alpha}. \quad (5.13)$$

It should be clear that whenever $\alpha \rightarrow \frac{1}{2}$, the spectrum becomes the 1D classical harmonic oscillator, i.e.,

$$E(\alpha = 1/2, n) = \frac{1}{2}mc^2 \left(\frac{\hbar}{mc}\right) \left(\frac{\pi}{2\sin(\pi/L)}\right) (n_x + 1). \quad (5.14)$$

6 The hypergeometric differential equation

The hypergeometric equation or Gauss’s differential equation has regular singular points at $x = 0, 1, \infty$. The equation has the form

$$x(1-x)\frac{d^2y}{dx^2} + [\gamma - (\alpha + \beta + 1)x]\frac{dy}{dx} - \alpha\beta y = 0, \quad (6.1)$$

where α, β , and γ are parameters[30, 31]. The terms $\gamma - (\alpha + \beta + 1)x$ and $-\alpha\beta$ approach

infinity (they diverge) when Eq.(6.1) is divided by $x(1-x)$ for $x = 0, 1, \infty$. For each regular singularity, it is possible to develop a unique series solution (about $x = 0, 1, \infty$) and hence we can rewrite Eq.(6.1) in a similar format for which solutions can be found[32].

Anyhow, there exist an alternative representation of Gauss's differential equation in the form of an intergral. The integral representation associated with the hypergeometric equation is given by,

$$\int_0^1 x^{\alpha-1}(1-x)^{\gamma-\alpha-1}(1-zx)^{-\beta} dx = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{k!} (\beta)_k \frac{(\alpha)_k \Gamma(\alpha) \Gamma(\gamma-\alpha)}{(\gamma)_k}. \quad (6.2)$$

Then, we have

$${}_2F_1(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, z) = \frac{\Gamma(\gamma)}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\gamma-\alpha)} \int_0^1 x^{\alpha-1}(1-x)^{\gamma-\alpha-1}(1-zx)^{-\beta} dx \quad H_{1,2}^{2,2} \left[z \left| \begin{matrix} (1-a, 1), (1-b, 1) \\ (0, 1), (1-c, 1) \end{matrix} \right. \right] = {}_2F_1(\alpha, \beta; \gamma; -z) \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)}{\Gamma(\gamma)}. \quad (6.3)$$

for the real part of α and $\gamma - \alpha$ greater than zero and $|z| < 1$. Note, if we let $z = 1$ then

$${}_2F_1(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, 1) = \frac{\Gamma(\gamma)}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\gamma-\alpha)} \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\gamma-\alpha-\beta)}{\Gamma(\gamma-\beta)}. \quad (6.4)$$

Gauss's differential equation has several different applications in physics, mathematics, and engineering. For example, consider Fox's H-function[33] which is defined as

$$H_{p,q}^{m,n}(z) = \left[z \left| \begin{matrix} (a_1, A_1), \dots, (a_p, A_P) \\ (b_1, B_1), \dots, (b_p, B_P) \end{matrix} \right. \right], \quad (6.5)$$

and

$$H_{p,q}^{m,n}(z) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_L \Theta(s) Z^{-s} ds, \quad (6.6)$$

where

$$\Theta(s) = \frac{\{\prod_{j=1}^m \Gamma(b_j + B_j s)\} \{\prod_{j=1}^n \Gamma(1 - a_j - A_j s)\}}{\{\prod_{j=m+1}^q \Gamma(1 - b_j - B_j s)\} \{\prod_{j=n+1}^p \Gamma(a_j + A_j s)\}} \quad (6.7)$$

This implies that Fox's H-function is based on the Mellin-Barnes integral transform which can be represented as ${}_2F_1(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, -z)$. Also, in Eq.(6.7), $i = (-1)^{1/2}$, $z \neq 0$, and $z^{-s} = e^{-s \ln |z| + i \arg z}$. It should also be emphasized that empty products must always be interpreted as "1" with $m, n, p, q \in \mathbb{N}_0$, $0 \leq n \leq p$, and $1 \leq m \leq q$. The term L on the integral is a suitable contour separating the poles; with $A_j, B_j \in \mathbb{R}_+$ and $a_j, b_j \in \mathbb{R}$. In essence, the H-function's[33] representation of the hypergeometric geometric equation is

6.1 The q -hypergeometric differential equation

In this section we shall use a suitable transformation and show that the 1D IDSQW can be expressed as the basic hypergeometric equation or q -hypergeometric differential equation. Therefore, if $R = \sin^2(x)$ then

$$\frac{d^2\psi(x)}{dx^2} = \sin^2(x) \frac{d^2\psi(x)}{dR^2} + 2 \cos(2x) \frac{d\psi(x)}{dR}. \quad (6.9)$$

Now consider Eq.(1.4),

$$\frac{d^2\psi(x)}{dx^2} + n^2\psi(x) = 0 \quad (6.10)$$

where

$$n^2 = \frac{2mE}{\hbar^2}, \quad (6.11)$$

then by substituting $\frac{d^2\psi}{dx^2}$ in Eq.(6.10) we get

$$\sin^2(x) \cos^2(x) \frac{d^2\psi(x)}{dR^2} + \frac{1}{2}(1 - 2\sin^2(x)) \frac{d\psi(x)}{dR} + \frac{n^2}{4}\psi(x) = 0 \quad (6.12)$$

and

$$R(1 - R) \frac{d^2\psi(x)}{dR^2} + \left(\frac{1}{2} - R\right) \frac{d\psi(x)}{dR} + \frac{n^2}{4}\psi(x) = \Upsilon = 0 \quad (6.13)$$

which is just the ordinary hypergeometric differential equation. Be that as it may, special functions such as Gauss's series solution and its differential equation can be expressed as a q -differential equation and a q -special function. If we focus solely on the former; this can be achieved by replacing the parameters in Gauss's differential equation by their q -analogs such that when $q \rightarrow 1$ the classical differential equation is recovered. Thus, given the previous prescription for developing Gauss's differential equation we may now write down the explicit form of the q -hypergeometric differential equation—a/k/a the basic hypergeometric differential equation—which is given by

$$R(q^\gamma - q^{\alpha+\beta+1}R)D_q^2\psi_q(x) + \frac{1 - q^\gamma}{1 - q}D_q\psi_q(x) + \left(\frac{(1 - q^\alpha)(1 - q^\beta)}{1 - q} - \frac{(1 - q^{\alpha+\beta+1})}{1 - q}R\right)D_q\psi_q(x) - \frac{(1 - q^\alpha)(1 - q^\beta)}{(1 - q)^2}\psi_q(x) = \Upsilon_q^{(Gauss)} = 0. \quad (6.14)$$

In the limit as $q \rightarrow 1$, we have that

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \Upsilon_q^{(Gauss)} = \Upsilon = 0 \quad (6.15)$$

where $\Upsilon_q^{(Gauss)}$ and Υ are the q -hypergeometric and hypergeometric differential equations, respectively.

The next thing we want to show before we discuss the spectrum and the solution of the q -hypergeometric differential equation is the limiting value of the third term in Eq.(6.14). If we let $\alpha\beta = \frac{n^2}{4}$ and take the limit as $q \rightarrow 1$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \frac{(1 - q^\alpha)(1 - q^\beta)}{(1 - q)^2} \psi_q(x) &= \lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \psi_q(x) \times \\ &\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \frac{(1 - q^\alpha)(1 - q^\beta)}{(1 - q)^2} = \\ \lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \frac{-q^{\alpha-1}(1 - q^\beta)\alpha - q^{\beta-1}(1 - q^\alpha)\beta}{2(q - 1)} &\times \lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \psi_q(x) \\ &= \frac{1}{2}[(\alpha + \beta)\alpha - \alpha^2]\psi(x) + \frac{1}{2}[(\alpha + \beta)\beta - \beta^2]\psi(x) \\ &= \frac{1}{2}\alpha\beta\psi(x) + \frac{1}{2}\alpha\beta\psi(x) = \alpha\beta\psi(x) \\ &= \frac{n^2}{4}\psi(x), \quad (6.16) \end{aligned}$$

and we recover the third term in Υ . A similar calculation—by taking the limit as $q \rightarrow 1$ —can be done on the other two trivial terms and the original terms are recovered as well.

The solution of $\Upsilon_q^{(Gauss)}$ is

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_q(x) &= \\ {}_2\phi_1(q^\alpha, q^\beta, q^\gamma; q, x) &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(q^\alpha; q)_n (q^\beta, q)_n}{(q; q)_n (q^\gamma; q)_n} x^n, \quad (6.17) \end{aligned}$$

where

$$(q^\alpha; q)_n = \begin{cases} 1, & n = 0, \\ (1 - q^\alpha)(1 - q^\alpha q) \dots (1 - q^\alpha q^{n-1}) & n = 1, 2, \dots, \end{cases} \quad (6.18)$$

is known as the q -shifted factorial. The energy eigenvalues are going to be similar

to the eigenvalues described in Subsection (4.3)—Eq.(4.24)—and are of the form,

$$E_q = \frac{\eta_q^2 \pi^2 \hbar^2}{2mL^2} \quad (\eta_q = [1]_q, [2]_q, \dots), \quad (6.19)$$

in the case of the asymmetric q -deformed 1D ISDQW.

6.2 The dynamical group and Lie algebra

Definition 6.1. A lie group G in the trivial sense, is a set of continuos symmetries. The set G must have two structures:

- (i) G must be a group; and
- (ii) G must be continuos,
 $\ni G \times G \longrightarrow G$ (the multiplicative map) and
 $G \longrightarrow G$ (the inversion map)[34].

An example of a Lie group G is realized from the angular momentum operators J_1, J_2 , and J_3 —the generators of infinitesimal rotations—which are nothing more than a continuous group of rotations.

Definition 6.2. A Lie algebra defined on a vector space Ξ , with elements (a, b, c, \dots) and Lie bracket $[\cdot, \cdot]$ is defined as:

- (i) $[a, b] \in \Xi$;
- (ii) $[a, b] = -[b, a]$; and
- (iii) $[a, [b, c]] + [b, [c, a]] + [c, [a, b]] = 0$
 $\forall a, b, c \in \Xi$.

The Lie group $U(2)$ is the group of rotations represented in two dimensional space generated by the corresponding $u(2)$ algebra. If we let $\underbrace{I_1, I_2, I_3, N}$ and $\underbrace{I_+, I_-, I_3, N}$ be the elements of the $u(2)$ Lie algebra with N being the usual number operator, $[I_i, N] = 0$ ($i = 1, 2, 3$), $[N, I_{\pm}] = 0$, and $I_i = I_i^\dagger$ —it follows that $su(2) \subset u(2)$, i.e., $su(2)(I_+, I_-, I_3)$ is a subalgebra of $u(2)$.

Since $\underbrace{I_+, I_-, I_3}$ are the generators of $SU(2)$ they must close under $[\cdot, \cdot] \ni$:(i) $[I_3, I_{\pm}] = \pm I_{\pm}$, and (ii) $[I_+, I_-] = 2I_3$. The q -analog of $SU(2)$ is $SU_q(2)$. The algebra is represented by the following commutator relationships:

$$[I_{\pm}, I_3] = \pm I_{\pm}, \quad (6.20)$$

and

$$[I_+, I_-] = \frac{q^{2I_3} - q^{-2I_3}}{q - q^{-1}} = [2I_3]_q. \quad (6.21)$$

Remark 3. $[I_+, I_-]$ is symmetric under the interchange of $q \longrightarrow \frac{1}{q}$.

The group $SU(1, 1)$ arises from analytic continuation of $\underbrace{I_+, I_-, I_3}$. The generators of this non-compact group are $\underbrace{K_+, K_-, K_3}$ which admit to the following commutator relationships:

$$[K_3, K_{\pm}] = \pm K_{\pm}, \quad (6.22)$$

and

$$[K_+, K_-] = -2K_3. \quad (6.23)$$

However, the dynamical group for the 1D ID-SQW—the asymmetric case—with respect to the transformed q -hypergeometric differential equation determined from the 1D Schrödinger equation is $SU(1, 1)$. Moreover, the dynamic Lie algebra of this system is $su(1, 1)$. Since we know the structure of the group and algebra in the undeformed case; this implies that $SU_q(1, 1)$ and $su_q(1, 1)$ are the q -deformed Lie group and Lie algebra, respectively.

The non-compact Lie group— $SU_q(1, 1)$ —and Lie algebra— $su_q(1, 1)$ —are

$$[K_3, K_{\pm}] = \pm K_{\pm} \quad (6.24)$$

and

$$[K_+, K_-] = \frac{q^{2K_3} - q^{-2K_3}}{q - q^{-1}} = -[2K_3]_q. \quad (6.25)$$

Note that $[2K_3]_q$ follows from **Lemma (3.1)** where $[x]_q$ is defined as the q -number. Anew, Eq.(6.25) is symmetric under the interchange of $q \rightarrow \frac{1}{q}$.

7 Conclusion

7.1 Concluding remarks

In this paper we discussed several methods for solving the 1D IDSQW—the Schrödinger equation in 1D. In Section (1), we conclude that the dynamic Lie group and Lie algebra are $SU(1, 1)$ and $su(1, 1)$ in the symmetric and asymmetric case. In addition, we showed that by use of SUSYQM (the factorization method), that despite having two dissimilar potentials (the 1D infinite potential and Pöschl-Teller potential), knowledge of the spectrum of the former gives complete information about the spectrum of the later. Again, $V_1(x)$ —Eq.(2.11)—encompasses the $SU(1, 1)$ and $su(1, 1)$ non-compact Lie group and Lie algebra, respectively.

Nevertheless, noninteger representations of the derivative as shown in Subsection (5.2) acquiesced a 1D spectrum—in the case when $\alpha \approx 1$ —for the quantum harmonic oscillator. Additionally, the difference between nonlocal and local operators in quantum mechanics can lead to the production of entirely new spectra—a consequence of nonlocality and memory effects.

The application of the Fourier derivative in Subsection (5.2) for $\alpha \approx 1$ —applied to the 1D IDSQW returned a fractional energy spectrum which is similar to the classical harmonic oscillator in the limit that $\alpha \rightarrow \frac{1}{2}$. Even though it was mentioned before that fractional derivatives are not unique, there exist an analog of the q -integer in fractional calculus that is independent of the definition of the fractional derivative. This analog is

called the fractional integer¹⁴, where

$$[n]_\alpha = 2^{1+\alpha} \pi^{\alpha/2} \left(\frac{\alpha \Gamma((1+\alpha)/2\alpha)}{\Gamma(1/2\alpha)} \right)^\alpha \times (\zeta(-\alpha, 1/4 + n/2) - \zeta(-\alpha, 3/4 + n/2)) = \pi^{\alpha/2} \left(\frac{\alpha \Gamma((1+\alpha)/2\alpha)}{\Gamma(1/2\alpha)} \right) E_\alpha(n + \frac{1}{2}). \quad (7.1)$$

It turns out that in the limit as $\alpha \rightarrow 1$, the spectrum of the harmonic oscillator is recovered which is similar to the spectrum recovered in Eq.(5.14).

Therefore, the dynamical group ($SU(2)_\alpha$) and Lie algebra of the 1D fractional Schrödinger equation—given J_+ , J_- , J_0 are the generators of the group—satisfy the following commutator relationships:

$$[J_0, J_\pm] = \pm J_\pm, \quad (7.2)$$

$$[J_+, J_-] = [2J_0]_\alpha, \quad (7.3)$$

with corresponding Casimir operator

$$C(SU_\alpha(2)) = [J]_\alpha [J + 1]_\alpha \quad (J = 0, 1, 2, \dots). \quad (7.4)$$

Bear in mind that both the non-compact group ($SU(1, 1)_\alpha$) and its Lie algebra can be obtained from analytic continuation of $U_\alpha(2)$.

Ultimately, we showed that it is possible to transform the 1D TISE so that it becomes the q -hypergeometric equation by using the substitution $R = \sin^2(x)$. In both the asymmetric and symmetric case for the 1D TISE, the dynamic Lie group and Lie algebra are $SU_q(1, 1)$ and $su_q(1, 1)$ which are the same for Subsection (4.3)—the 1D q -Schrödinger equation. We should also mention that we have completely neglected continuum states in our analysis which are included in the unitary irreducible representations illustrated in Eqs.(7.5–7.8)—the building blocks of the spectrum generating algebra—since we are dealing with a simple quantum system (1D

¹⁴The fractional integer contains the so-called incomplete Reimann or Hurwitz zeta functions.

IDSQW). The aforesaid unitary irreducible representations—*unirreps*—are given by:

$$D^+(k) \begin{cases} q = -k + m, & m = 0, 1, 2, \dots \\ k < 0 \end{cases} \quad (7.5)$$

$$D^-(k) \begin{cases} q = k + m, & m = 0, -1, -2, \dots \\ k < 0 \end{cases} \quad (7.6)$$

$$D_s(Q, q_0) \begin{cases} q = q_0 + m, & m = 0, \pm 1, \dots \\ Q < 0 |q_0| (|q_0| - 1), & q_0 \in (\frac{-1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}) \end{cases} \quad (7.7)$$

$$D_P(Q, q_0) \begin{cases} q = q_0 + m, & m = 0, \pm 1, \dots \\ Q = -\beta^2 - \frac{1}{4}, & q_0 \in (\frac{-1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}), \end{cases} \quad (7.8)$$

where $D_P(Q, q_0)$ and $D_s(Q, q_0)$ are the principal and supplementary series of the *unirreps*, respectively—both are unbounded. While $D^-(k)$ and $\underbrace{D^+(k)}$ are bounded *unirreps*—in particular, we were only concerned with $D^+(k)$.

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